

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 62 (2025) 294-306

EISSN 2543-5426

The Effect of Toad Venom on Some Hematological and Biochemical Parameters in Albino Wistar Rats

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ABSTRACT

This research evaluated the impact of toad venom on certain hematological and biochemical parameters in albino Wistar rats. A total of twenty male albino Wistar rats, each weighing between 120 and 150 g, were utilized in this investigation. They were divided into four groups. The control group received distilled water, while the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th groups were administered 100 mg/kg, 150 mg/kg, and 200 mg/kg of toad venom orally, respectively. Blood samples were obtained after 24, 48, and 72 hours through ocular puncture into EDTA and plain containers for hematological and biochemical evaluations. The findings indicated a statistically significant decrease in red blood cell count and hemoglobin levels ($p < 0.05$) compared to the control group. The results also revealed an increase in white blood cell count and its differentials, heightened levels of alanine transaminase (ALT) and aspartate transaminase (AST), and elevated potassium levels ($p < 0.05$) relative to the control group (hyperkalemia). All these effects intensified with a rise in the dosage of toad venom. Additionally, there was a minor increase in creatinine and urea, which was statistically insignificant. In summary, the consumption of toad venom in rats resulted in a reduction in RBC and Hb (erythrocyte) counts, elevated WBC counts, and liver enzyme abnormalities based on their values under the experimental conditions noted. Key Words: Toad venom, hematological and biochemical parameters, health implications.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Toads are amphibians belonging to the order Anura, family Bufonidae, and genus Bufo. They are widespread globally but primarily inhabit regions with tropical and moist temperate climates, with each area hosting specific toad species. Across the globe, there are 34 genera and 420 species of toads (Qian Yang et al., 2015). The most commonly toxic species within the Bufo genus include *Bufo merinus*, *B. typhonitus*, *B. crucifer*, *B. alvaries*, and *B. regularis*. Toad venom is released from the parotid and skin glands of the toad when they feel threatened (Qian Yang et al., 2015). These glands fall into two categories: mucous glands and granular glands (Hickman et al., 1995). Mucous glands are distributed all over the toad's body and produce a clear mucus that serves as a lubricant in water, as well as containing various glycoproteins such as mucins and carbohydrate residues like galactose, fructose, and sialic acid. In contrast, granular glands are more specialized (Hickman et al., 1995), containing centrally located nuclei and secreting toxins that protect against predators, including birds, mammals, snakes, and crocodiles that attempt to consume them. Toad venom includes cardioactive compounds (bufadienolides like bufotoxin, bufalin, butogen, and bufotalin) that have effects comparable to those of cardiac glycosides (Heerden & Steyn, 1998; Maris, 1992; Hiral et al., 1992). Additionally, peptides and proteins found in the venom of *Bombina orientalis* demonstrate antimicrobial properties, enzymatic functions, and aid in healing cuts or wounds (Gibson et al., 1991). Other components of toad venom encompass biogenic amines (indolealkylamines), catecholamines, alkaloids, and steroids (Basir et al., 2000).

The physiological impact of toad venom includes the inhibition of sodium-potassium adenosine triphosphatase (Na^+/K^+ -ATPase). The blockade of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase plays a role in maintaining water and electrolyte balance. The toxin from toads exerts a positive inotropic effect and modifies the heart muscle's electrophysiology by attaching to and inhibiting Na^+/K^+ -ATPase located on the surface membrane of myocardial cells. When Na^+/K^+ -ATPase is inhibited, the sodium-calcium exchanger expels excess intracellular sodium in favor of calcium. This exchange increases calcium levels in the sarcoplasm and is responsible for the positive inotropic effect observed with digitalis. Additionally, inhibition of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase leads to elevated extracellular potassium levels, resulting in hyperkalemia. At toxic doses, the disruption of electrolyte balance caused by the toad toxin can induce nausea, vomiting, general malaise, tachy-bradyarrhythmia, cardiopulmonary arrest, and potentially death (Dae et al., 2007).

Anjoo et al. (2013) demonstrated that bufadienolides can inhibit Na^+/K^+ -ATPase, with a particular affinity for its alpha-1 isoform. This ability allows them to share similar effects with other cardiac glycosides, such as increasing sodium excretion, inducing vasoconstriction that can lead to hypertension, and serving as cardiac inotropes.

Another study by Francisco et al. (2012) indicated that bufalin has natriuretic and diuretic effects in rat kidneys (both in vivo and in vitro) via the inhibition of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase in situations of salt overload. Their natriuretic actions and the fundamental mechanism involved is the suppression of renal Na^+/K^+ -ATPase, which decreases sodium transport from the renal tubular ultrafiltrate to the peritubular blood.

Camplesi et al. (2013) discussed the hematological and biochemical impacts of toad venom, assessing the clinical and laboratory findings in dogs that were exposed to it. They noted that 53% of the intoxicated dogs had a reduced red blood cell count, 40% experienced neutropenia, 26% had lymphopenia, and 20% displayed urea values below the reference range, indicating that bufotoxin does not adversely affect renal function and is therefore regarded as

non-nephrotoxic. Mild elevations of alanine transaminase (ALT) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) levels were also observed in this group, attributed to the hepatic metabolism of the toad venom (Camplesi et al., 2013). Ashok et al. (2011) reported a case involving a 26-year-old male who was admitted to the surgical unit due to abdominal pain and vomiting following toad ingestion. The examination revealed leukocytosis, elevated serum amylase, normal levels of urea and creatinine, a serum sodium of 133 meq/L, and potassium levels rising to 5.7 mmol/L. Barbosa et al. (2009) studied the effects of toad poisoning in three dogs, which displayed leukocytosis, neutrophilia, monocytosis, increased total plasma protein, along with elevated urea, creatinine, ALT, ALP, and gamma-glutamyltransferase, while potassium levels remained normal. When humans and animals ingest toad venom, it can result in various symptoms including pain and intense irritation in the throat, nose, and eyes (Ott, 2001); hallucinogenic effects can also occur when the chopped skins of the toad are smoked (Bardose et al., 2009; David Spoerke, 2015). Additional physiological impacts include cardiovascular, respiratory, gastrointestinal, neurological, and hematological effects, such as ventricular fibrillation, arrhythmias, vasoconstriction, heart block, difficulty breathing, respiratory failure, paralysis, seizures, numbness, excessive salivation, vomiting, abdominal discomfort, and cyanosis (Ott, 2001; Bardose et al., 2009; David Spoerke, 2015). Given the documented adverse effects of toad venom, it is essential to explore its influence on hematological and biochemical factors through a rat model; this could hold significant medical relevance for humans.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at the Department of Human Physiology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Okofia Campus. The biochemical parameters were assessed at Imo State Teaching Hospital, Orlu, while hematological parameters were evaluated at Mbanjo Joint Hospital, Isiala Mbanjo, Imo State.

2. 1. Experimental Animals

Twenty toads of the *Bufo regularis* species were identified by Dr. Ajero from the Department of Animal and Environmental Sciences, Imo State University, Owerri, and were utilized for venom extraction. The venom was manually extracted from the parotid gland with the assistance of a team member who positioned a sterile glass plate to catch the secretion as it was expelled. The collected venom on the sterile glass plate was combined, weighed, and the appropriate amount was diluted in distilled water to achieve the desired milligram concentration. Inbred male albino Wistar rats (a total of 20), weighing between 120 g and 150 g, were obtained from the Animal House of the Department of Human Physiology at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Okofia Campus, Nigeria. The rats were housed in standard well-ventilated cages maintained at a temperature range of 27 – 29 °C, and were provided with water and standard laboratory chow (Vital Top Feed, Jos, Nigeria). They had unrestricted access to food and water troughs. Remaining feed and water were discarded, and the cages were disinfected with a chlorhexidine antiseptic solution every 12 hours. Animals were kept under a light and dark cycle of 12 hours each. The animals were allowed to acclimatize for two weeks prior to being divided into groups. They were randomly allocated into four groups, each consisting of five rats that weighed between 120 g and 150 g. Group 1 functioned as the control and was given 0.3 mL of distilled water. Groups 2, 3, and 4 received doses of 100 mg/kg, 150 mg/kg,

and 200 mg/kg of toad venom, respectively. The venom was administered orally using a cannula. Afterward, the animals were anesthetized with chloroform, and a micro-hematocrit tube was used for ocular puncture.

Blood samples were gathered directly into EDTA bottles for hematological assessments and into plain bottles for biochemical examinations at intervals of 24 hours, 48 hours, and 72 hours. Ethical clearance was obtained from the College of Medicine Ethical Committee at Nnamdi Azikiwe University. The treatment of the rats adhered to the guidelines established by the Institutional Animal Medical Ethics, Bio-safety and Bio-security Committee (IAMEBBC) (No. 33/320/IAMEBBC/IBSC). The hematological parameters assessed included the white blood cell count, differential count, hemoglobin levels, and red blood cell count. These parameters were evaluated using a modified automated approach (Wallace H. Coulter, United Kingdom, 1998). The biochemical parameters analyzed comprised:

- 1) Alanine transaminase (ALT) and aspartate transaminase (AST) were assessed using the Modified Reitman and Frankel technique (Reitman & Frankel, 1957).
- 2) Creatinine levels were measured using the Modified Jaffe’s method (Jaffe, 1886).
- 3) Urea concentrations were determined by using the Modified Urease Berthelot method (Berthelot, 2004).
- 4) Electrolyte levels: Sodium ions were evaluated using the Modified Colorimetric Method, while potassium ions were assessed via the Colorimetric Method of Jacob & Hoffman (1931).

2. 2. Data Analysis

The results were presented in tables. Data were subjected to statistical analysis using the Student’s t-test in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 21. Mean ± SEM were calculated, and mean values were considered statistically significant at 95% confidence level ($p \leq 0.05$).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Hematological Parameters

3. 1. 1. Hemoglobin (Hb)

There was a decrease in hemoglobin concentration in the intoxicated groups at 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs when compared with the control group, and it was statistically significant. This is shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Effect of toad venom on hemoglobin concentration in albino rats after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs of administration.

Group/Dose	Group/dose	Mean ±Sem	P- Value (0.05)	Test of Sig.
24 hours	1 (control)	14.80 ± 0.37		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	11.20 ± 0.13	0.046	P.<0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	10.50 ± 0.03	0.042	P.<0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	9.00 ± 0.05	0.043	P.<0.05

48 hours	1 (control)	15.20 ± 0.32	0.043 0.040 0.041	P.<0.05 P.<0.05 P.<0.05
	2 (100 mg/kg)	11.00 ± 0.13		
	3 (150 mg/kg)	9.80 ± 0.03		
	4 (200 mg/kg)	8.60 ± 0.04		
72 hours	1 (control)	14.20 ± 0.35	0.038 0.042 0.039	P.<0.05 P.<0.05 P.<0.05
	2 (100 mg/kg)	10.94 ± 0.12		
	3 (150 mg/kg)	9.64 ± 0.02		
	4 (200 mg/kg)	7.62 ± 0.05		

3. 1. 2. Red Blood Cell (RBC)

There was a decrease in the red blood cell count in the intoxicated groups at 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs when compared with the control group. This decrease was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2. Effect of toad venom on RBC after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs.

Hour	Group/dose	Mean ±Sem	P-value ($p = 0.05$)	Test of Sig.
24 hours	1 (control)	8.11 ± 0.46	0.033 0.040 0.031	P.<0.05 P.<0.05 P.<0.05
	2 (100 mg/kg)	6.25 ± 0.09		
	3 (150 mg/kg)	6.01 ± 0.05		
	4 (200 mg/kg)	5.69 ± 0.16		
48 hours	1 (control)	9.02 ± 0.48	0.034 0.028 0.030	P.<0.05 P.<0.05 P.<0.05
	2 (100 mg/kg)	6.00 ± 0.08		
	3 (150 mg/kg)	5.01 ± 0.07		
	4 (200 mg/kg)	4.05 ± 0.07		
72 hours	1 (control)	9.00 ± 0.45	0.031 0.031 0.030	P.<0.05 P.<0.05 P.<0.05
	2 (100 mg/kg)	5.00 ± 0.08		
	3 (150 mg/kg)	4.02 ± 0.10		
	4 (200 mg/kg)	3.00 ± 0.09		

3. 1. 3. White Blood Cell (WBC)

There was an increase in WBC in the groups of rats intoxicated with toad venom at 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs when compared with the control group. This increase was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 3. Effect of toad venom on WBC after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs.

Hour	Group/dose	Mean ±Sem	P-value ($p = 0.05$)	Test of Sig.
24 hours	1 (control)	11020.6 ± 314.72	0.021	P.<0.05
	2 (100 mg/kg)	12623.4 ± 162.95		

	3 (150 mg/kg)	12992.0 ± 76.82	0.020	P.<0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	12935.0 ± 396.13	0.022	P.<0.05
48 hours	1 (control)	11030.8 ± 310.71		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	13453.8 ± 193.31	0.024	P.<0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	13928.0 ± 139.38	0.023	P.<0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	13909.0 ± 75.30	0.020	P.<0.05
72 hours	1 (control)	12010.3 ± 331.60		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	14529.6 ± 144.15	0.030	P.<0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	14710.8 ± 151.89	0.024	P.<0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	35074.0 ± 200.93	0.056	P.>0.05

3. 1. 4. Neutrophils

The neutrophil count increased in the rats that received toad venom after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs. This increase was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 4. Effect of toad venom on neutrophil count after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs.

Hours	Group/Dose	MEAN ±SEM	P-value ($p = 0.05$)	Test of Sig.
24 hours	1 (control)	70.33 ± 0.60		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	80.33 ± 0.60	0.025	P.<0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	82.50 ± 0.28	0.024	P.<0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	85.16 ± 0.44	0.020	P.<0.05
48 hours	1 (control)	71.32 ± 0.70		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	82.80 ± 0.15	0.022	P.<0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	84.00 ± 0.28	0.022	P.<0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	87.00 ± 0.28	0.023	P.<0.05
72 hours	1 (control)	69.70 ± 0.81		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	82.80 ± 0.23	0.020	P.<0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	85.66 ± 0.24	0.020	P.<0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	90.33 ± 0.60	0.018	P.<0.05

3. 1. 5. Lymphocytes

The lymphocyte count decreased in the groups of rats that ingested toad venom at 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs. This decrease was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 5. Effect of toad venom on lymphocyte count after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs.

Hours	Group/Dose	Mean ±Sem	P-value ($p = 0.05$)	Test of Sig.
24 hours	1 (control)	19.80 ± 0.15		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	20.06 ± 0.34	0.040	P.<0.05

	3 (150 mg/kg)	21.10 ± 0.20	0.041	P.<0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	22.90 ± 0.20	0.040	P.<0.05
48 hours	1 (control)	18.50 ± 0.12		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	22.43 ± 0.23	0.040	P.<0.05
	3(150 mg/kg)	24.46 ± 0.26	0.042	P.<0.05
	4(200 mg/kg)	26.15 ± 0.17	0.039	P.<0.05
72 hours	1 (control)	20.01 ± 0.14		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	29.0 0 ± 0.25	0.039	P.<0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	30.48 ± 0.27	0.039	P.<0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	31.75 ± 0.625	0.038	P.<0.05

3. 2. Biochemical Parameters

3. 2. 1. Sodium Ion (Na⁺)

There was a slight decrease in sodium ion levels at 48 hrs and 72 hrs when compared with the control group. This decrease was statistically insignificant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 6. Effect of toad venom on Na⁺ after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs.

Hours	Group/Dose	Mean ±Sem	P-value (p = 0.05)	Test of Sig.
24 hours	1 (control)	145.79 ± 1.62		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	145.30 ± 2.39	0.870	P.>0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	144.50 ± 1.84	0.780	P.>0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	144.60 ± 1.29	0.650	P.>0.05
48 hours	1 (control)	143.80 ± 1.72		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	143.04 ± 0.58	0.866	P.>0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	143.13 ± 1.13	0.686	P.>0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	143.29 ± 1.33	0.661	P.>0.05
72 hours	1 (control)	144.90 ± 1.64		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	142.40 ± 0.51	0.785	P.>0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	143.63 ± 0.75	0.875	P.>0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	141.92 ± 1.51	0.578	P.>0.05

3. 2. 2. Potassium Ion (K⁺)

There was an increase in the potassium level of rats that ingested toad venom after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs. The increase was statistically insignificant at 24 hrs but became statistically significant after 48 hrs and 72 hrs.

Table 7. Effect of toad venom on potassium level in albino rats after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs.

Hours	Group/Dose	MEAN ±SEM	P-value (p = 0.05)	Test of Sig.
24 hours	1 (control)	4.89 ± 0.38	0.894 0.572 0.631	P.>0.05 P.>0.05 P.>0.05
	2 (100 mg/kg)	4.99 ± 1.01		
	3 (150 mg/kg)	5.12 ± 0.32		
	4 (200 mg/kg)	5.28 ± 0.48		
48 hours	1 (control)	3.90 ± 0.44	0.019 0.021 0.020	P.<0.05 P.<0.05 P.<0.05
	2 (100 mg/kg)	5.81 ± 0.09		
	3 (150 mg/kg)	5.88 ± 0.04		
	4 (200 mg/kg)	7.92 ± 0.39		
72 hours	1 (control)	4.50 ± 0.46	0.020 0.016 0.022	P.<0.05 P.<0.05 P.<0.05
	2 (100 mg/kg)	7.48 ± 0.28		
	3 (150 mg/kg)	6.89 ± 1.02		
	4 (200 mg/kg)	7.68 ± 0.52		

3. 2. 3. Alanine Transaminase (ALT)

The value of alanine transaminase (ALT) increased in the groups of rats treated with toad venom after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs. This increase was statistically significant at p < 0.05.

Table 8. Effect of toad venom on ALT after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs.

Hours	Group/Dose	MEAN ±SEM	P-value (p = 0.05)	Test of Sig.
24 hours	1 (control)	68.99 ± 1.23	0.021 0.020 0.021	P.<0.05 P.<0.05 P.<0.05
	2 (100 mg/kg)	76.77 ± 0.83		
	3 (150 mg/kg)	79.92 ± 0.72		
	4 (200 mg/kg)	80.12 ± 0.47		
48 hours	1 (control)	70.51 ± 1.14	0.021 0.020 0.020	P.<0.05 P.<0.05 P.<0.05
	2 (100 mg/kg)	78.12 ± 0.69		
	3 (150 mg/kg)	80.80 ± 0.68		
	4 (200 mg/kg)	81.08 ± 0.61		
72 hours	1 (control)	67.53 ± 1.32	0.021 0.020 0.019	P.<0.05 P.<0.05 P.<0.05
	2 (100 mg/kg)	79.37 ± 0.53		
	3 (150 mg/kg)	81.48 ± 0.84		
	4 (200 mg/kg)	84.32 ± 0.99		

3. 2. 4. Aspartate Transaminase (AST)

The value of aspartate transaminase (AST) increased in the groups of albino rats intoxicated with toad venom after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs. This increase was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 9. Effect of toad venom on AST after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs.

Hours	Group/Dose	MEAN \pm SEM	P-value ($p = 0.05$)	Test of Sig.
24 hours	1 (control)	56.53 \pm 0.90		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	81.31 \pm 1.23	0.021	P.<0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	83.83 \pm 1.23	0.020	P.<0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	84.60 \pm 0.60	0.020	P.<0.05
48 hour	1 (control)	55.74 \pm 0.90		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	83.30 \pm 1.00	0.020	P.<0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	84.89 \pm 1.00	0.020	P.<0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	87.29 \pm 0.38	0.020	P.<0.05
72 hours	1 (control)	59.46 \pm 0.91		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	85.32 \pm 0.75	0.020	P.<0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	86.70 \pm 0.65	0.020	P.<0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	94.75 \pm 1.18	0.019	P.<0.05

3. 2. 5. Creatinine

There was a slight increase in creatinine levels in the groups of rats treated with toad venom when compared with the control. This increase was statistically insignificant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 10. Effect of toad venom on creatinine level after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs.

Hours	Groups/Dose	Mean \pm Sem	P-value ($p = 0.05$)	Test of Sig.
24 hours	1 (control)	0.82 \pm 0.03		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	0.81 \pm 0.01	0.101	P.>0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	0.82 \pm 0.00	0.210	P.>0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	0.82 \pm 0.02	0.061	P.>0.05
48 hours	1 (control)	0.83 \pm 0.03		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	0.82 \pm 0.06	0.110	P.>0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	0.83 \pm 0.02	0.410	P.>0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	0.83 \pm 0.05	0.121	P.>0.05
72 hours	1 (control)	0.83 \pm 0.04		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	0.83 \pm 0.05	0.062	P.>0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	0.82 \pm 0.06	0.410	P.>0.05
	4 (200 mg/ kg)	0.83 \pm 0.03	0.121	P.>0.05

3. 2 .6. Urea

There was a slight decrease in urea levels in the groups of rats treated with toad venom when compared with the control. This decrease was statistically not significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 11. Effect of toad venom on urea level after 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs.

Hours	Group/Dose	MEAN \pm SEM	P-value ($p = 0.05$)	Test of Sig.
24 hours	1 (control)	11.08 \pm 1.23		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	11.08 \pm 0.83	0.421	P.>0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	11.07 \pm 0.72	0.051	P.>0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	11.06 \pm 0.47	0.321	P.>0.05
48 hours	1 (control)	11.08 \pm 1.21		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	11.07 \pm 0.69	0.071	P.>0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	11.08 \pm 0.68	0.082	P.>0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	11.08 \pm 0.61	0.062	P.>0.05
72 hours	1 (control)	11.09 \pm 1.24		
	2 (100 mg/kg)	11.09 \pm 0.53	0.100	P.>0.05
	3 (150 mg/kg)	11.06 \pm 0.84	0.121	P.>0.05
	4 (200 mg/kg)	11.08 \pm 0.99	0.310	P.>0.05

4. DISCUSSION

The toad is an amphibian that is widely found around the globe. When threatened or stimulated, a toad releases venom from its parotid and skin glands, which serves as a protective measure against predators (Clark, 1997). Research has indicated that toad venom possesses hallucinogenic, cardiovascular, neurological, gastrointestinal, respiratory, and antimicrobial properties, leading to effects such as arrhythmia, ventricular fibrillation, heart block, numbness, paralysis, seizures, and even death (Barbosa et al., 2013; David, 2015). Thus, it is crucial to examine its impact on hematological and biochemical parameters in rats to better understand how it operates.

Shortly after the administration of toad venom, the treated animals exhibited decreased activity (they appeared dull and weak) but progressively regained strength within 48 hours post-administration. This observation may result from gastrointestinal and neurological effects associated with the ingestion of toad venom, as indicated in (Bardose et al., 2009; Camplesi et al., 2013; David Spoeke, 2015).

This finding aligns with the study conducted by (Bardose et al., 2009) on toad poisoning in three dogs, which displayed intense salivation, vomiting, respiratory distress, diarrhea, and seizures. It also corresponds with David, (2015), who investigated toad poisoning in cats and dogs, noting that they exhibited neurological and gastrointestinal symptoms such as reduced activity, paralysis, seizures, salivation, and vomiting due to the local anesthetic effects of bufagins and irritation of the oral mucosa. The evaluation of erythrocytes revealed a decrease in the red blood cell count and hemoglobin concentration in all groups treated with toad venom compared to the control group.

These reductions became more pronounced over time. The decline in hemoglobin and red blood cells may result from an increased rate of red blood cell destruction or a decreased rate of production, potentially due to significant erythrocyte damage or inhibition of erythrocyte formation. This finding aligns with the research conducted by Anjoo et al. (2013) on dogs that were intoxicated with toad venom, where the results demonstrated a decrease in red blood cells and packed cell volume, attributed to the anorexia and gastroenteritis observed in the dogs post-intoxication.

The observed reduction in hemoglobin and red blood cells might also be associated with impaired hepatic heme biosynthesis, given that toad venom could induce liver cell injury. Additionally, blockage of the Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase could contribute to the decrease in hemoglobin and red blood cells. Inhibition of the Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase pump may elevate intracellular osmolarity, leading to osmotic water uptake into the cell. This process can cause the cell to swell and ultimately rupture (Dae et al., 2007).

The reduction in red blood cells and hemoglobin is consistent with earlier studies conducted by (Dae et al., 2007; Francisco et al., 2012; Camplesi et al., 2013; Anjoo et al., 2013). An increase in total white blood cell count (leucocytosis) was observed, with notable neutrophilia and lymphocytosis in the white blood cell differential counts of the rats treated with toad venom. This finding correlates with the studies by Barbosa et al. (2009) Ashok et al. (2011). The rise in white blood cell count may be attributed to the activation of defense mechanisms and the immune response aimed at eliminating bufotoxin. It could also stem from inflammatory reactions in the gastrointestinal tract, resulting in symptoms such as anorexia, vomiting, and irritation (Barbosa et al., 2009; Ashok et al., 2011; David Spoerke, 2015).

The biochemical assessment revealed elevated liver enzymes (AST & ALT) in the rats administered toad venom compared to the untreated group. These results align with findings reported by Barbosa et al. (2009) and Camplesi et al. (2013). It was also noted that the rise in AST and ALT levels was linked to increasing doses of toad venom. Given that bufotoxin is metabolized in the liver, the elevation of AST and ALT likely indicates liver cell injury or damage caused by bufotoxin, leading to the release of these enzymes from the cells. The analysis of electrolytes indicated hyperkalemia and a minor reduction in sodium levels among the rats exposed to toad venom when compared to the control group. This corresponds with findings from Robert & Peterson (2001), Camplesi et al. (2013) Anjoo et al. (2013).

Hyperkalemia can be attributed to the inhibitory effect of toad venom on Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase (Dae et al., 2007). No significant variations were observed in the levels of urea and creatinine in the rats treated with toad venom compared to the control group. This is consistent with the findings of Camplesi et al. (2013), indicating that toad venom does not impact kidney function.

5. CONCLUSION

Toad venom resulted in inflammation, a decrease in hemoglobin, liver damage, elevated potassium levels, and various gastrointestinal and neurological alterations that could be life-threatening and potentially fatal at extremely high toxic concentrations. The venom does not cause renal damage and can be classified as non-nephrotoxic based on the values observed under the current experimental conditions. Given the metabolic impact of toad venom on liver cells, it is recommended that histopathological examinations be conducted on hepatic cells to assess whether the effects would be more beneficial or detrimental to humans.

References

- [1] Ablishek, D. G., Hippargi, R. V., & Gandhare, A. N. (2007). Toad skin secretions: Potent source of pharmacologically and therapeutically significant compounds. *The Internet Journal of Pharmacology*, 5(2), 1–7
- [2] Anjoo, K., Rathour, A., & Kaur, M. (2013). Bufadienolides and their medicinal utility. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 5(4), 20–27
- [3] Arnaud-Batista, F. J., Costa, G. T., Barbosa de Oliveira, I. M., Costa, P. P. C., Santos, C. F., Tonteles, M. C., ... Nascimento, N. R. F. (2012). Natriuretic effect of bufalin in isolated rat kidneys involves activation of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase–Src kinase pathway. *American Journal of Physiology – Renal Physiology*, 302(8), F959-F967
- [4] Awasthi, K. (2006). Biocontrol backfire. *Down to Earth*, 15(5), 7-9
- [5] Barbosa, C. M., Medeiros, M. S., Riani, C., Camlesi, A., & Sakate, M. (2009). Venomous animals and toxins including tropical diseases. *Journal of Venomous Animals and Toxins including Tropical Diseases*, 15(3), 12–20. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1678-91992009000300002>
- [6] Basir, Y. J., Knoop, F. C., Dulka, J., & Conlon, M. J. (2000). Multiple antimicrobial peptides and peptides related to bradykinin and neuromedin N isolated from skin secretion of the toad. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta*, 1543(1), 95-105
- [7] Berthelot, M. (2013). Modified urease-Berthelot method of serum urea estimation. *UK Pointe Scientific*, 5(4), 1-14
- [8] Camplesi, A. C., Simão, N. M., Sakate, M., Sobreira, M. F., Bersano, P. R., & Freitas, S. H. (2010). Clinical and laboratory evaluation of dogs experimentally intoxicated with toad venom. *Journal of Venomous Animals and Toxins including Tropical Diseases*, 16(2), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1678-91992010000200014>
- [9] Clark, B. T. (1997). The natural history of amphibian skin secretions: Their normal functioning and potential medical applications. *Biological Reviews*, 72(3), 365–379.
- [10] Dae, W. H., Taek, G. K., Young, K., & Jang, H. B. (2007). Toad venom poisoning resembling digitalis intoxication and hyperkalemia. *Korean Circulation Journal*, 37(5), 283–286.
- [11] David, S. (2015). Toad toxins. *Erowid*, 15(3), 4–10
- [12] Dong, Z. Q., Zhao, Z., Wei, Z. W., & Yun, K. Y. (2013). Bufalin, a component in Chansu, inhibits proliferation and invasion of hepatocellular carcinoma cells. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 13, 185. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-13-185>
- [13] Enrique, D., & Deulofeu, V. (1944). The basic constituents of the venom of some South American toads. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 153(9), 459–463
- [14] Garg, A. D., Hippargi, R. V., & Gandhare, A. N. (2007). Toad skin secretions: Potent source of pharmacologically and therapeutically significant compounds. *The Internet Journal of Pharmacology*, 5(2), 1–7

- [15] Gibson, B. W., Tang, D., Mandrell, R., Kelly, M., & Spindel, E. R. (1991). Bombinin-like peptides with antimicrobial activity from skin secretion of the Asian toad, *Bombina orientalis*. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 266(34), 23103–23111
- [16] Hickman, C. P., Roberts, L. S., & Larson, A. (1995). *Integrated principles of zoology* (9th ed.). W. C. Brown Publishers.
- [17] Jacob, H. R. D., & Hoffman, W. S. (1931). A new colorimetric method for the estimation of potassium. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 24(7), 12–55
- [18] Jaffe, M. (1886). Über den Niederschlag, welchen Pikrinsäure in normalen Harn erzeugt und über eine neue Reaktion des Kreatinins. *Zeitschrift für Physiologische Chemie*, 10(5), 391–400.
- [19] Li, C., Hashimi, S. M., Cao, S., Mellick, A. S., Wei, M. Q., & Good, D. (2013). The mechanisms of Chansu in inducing efficient apoptosis in colon cancer cells. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2013, 1–12
- [20] Pinya, L., Qiongtao, S., Tao, L., Zhonglin, W., Xuan, Z., & Ying, Z., et al. (2014). Inhibitory effect of cinobufagin on L-type Ca²⁺ currents, contractility, and Ca²⁺ homeostasis of isolated adult rat ventricular myocytes. *The Scientific World Journal*, 2014, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/496765>
- [21] Qian, Y., Zhou, X., Zhang, M., Bai, L., Shan, M., Wei, C., ... Wang, S. (2015). Angel of human health: Current research updates in toad medicine. *American Journal of Translational Research*, 7(1), 1–14
- [22] Reitman, S., & Frankel, S. (1957). A colorimetric method for the determination of serum glutamic oxalacetic and glutamic pyruvic transaminases. *American Journal of Clinical Pathology*, 28(1), 56–63. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcp/28.1.56>
- [23] Sakate, M., & Lucas, P. C. (2000). Toad envenoming in dogs: Effects and treatment. *Journal of Venomous Animals and Toxins including Tropical Diseases*, 6(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0104-79302000000100003>
- [24] Sandroni, P. (2001). Aphrodisiacs past and present: A historical review. *Clinical Autonomic Research*, 11(5), 303–307. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02332975>
- [25] Steyn, P. S., & Van Heerden, F. R. (1998). Bufadienolides of plant and animal origin. *Natural Product Reports*, 15(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1039/A815017Y>
- [26] Wallace, H. C. (1998). Modified Wallace H. Coulter method of FBC. *PubMed Laboratory*, 23(8), 45–98
- [27] Won, S. Y., Kim, J., Lee, Y. W., Yoon, D. H., Cho, C. K., & Yoo, H. S. (2009). Toxicity studies on *Secretiobufonis*, a traditional supplement in Asia. *Journal of Acupuncture and Meridian Studies*, 2(2), 159–164. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2005-2901\(09\)60045-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2005-2901(09)60045-7)
- [28] Yang, Q., Zhou, X., Zhang, M., Bai, L., Shan, M., Wei, C., ... Wang, S. (2015). Angel of human health: Current research updates in toad medicine. *American Journal of Translational Research*, 7(1), 1–14